

SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF KNOWLEDGE ON SPORTS AESTHETICS IN FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical-methodological foundations of the development of knowledge about sports aesthetics in future physical education teachers, the practical methodical system of developing knowledge about sports aesthetics, and the effectiveness of developing knowledge about sports aesthetics have been studied. Motives for developing knowledge of sports aesthetics among future physical education teachers were also analyzed.

Key words: pedagogue, physical education, sports aesthetics, sport, technology, didactic, modernization, integration, cluster approach, fossilization education, reflexive, interactive, training, innovative, integrative.

INTRODUCTION. Today, scientific research is being carried out on the organization of a healthy lifestyle. This created an opportunity to strengthen the scientific and theoretical foundations of this process. Therefore, attention to sports in our country is extremely serious, and the number of people engaged in sports and physical education is also increasing. Sport is a set of actions that ensure human health. However, a healthy lifestyle is not formed only through sports, it also requires aesthetic education. Because a person needs both physical and spiritual education. Because in this regard, the principle "Healthy body - healthy mind" does not apply for nothing.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. The research of the pedagogical and psychological foundations of the development of the knowledge of sports aesthetics in future physical education teachers can be classified into three parts: studying in Uzbekistan, CIS countries and Western countries.

Uzbek scientists N.N. Tokhtaboyev, A.N. Shopulatov, S.S. Tajibayev, F. Kerimov, A. Shopulatov, A. Muzaffarov, A. Mirzayev, A. Khudoyorov work on the development of professional skills of physical education and sports specialists, formation of moral values in athletes. issues of effective organization are studied. Also, the scientific researches of S.Kh. Fayzulina, S.K. Annamuratova, A. Hasanov, F. Zorayev, A. Vosikhov, A. Sulaymonov, K. Dosimov have highlighted the educational possibilities of aesthetic education and sports aesthetics.

In Western countries, the issues of directing young people to the process of mass sports rehabilitation, rational use of the possibilities of sports aesthetics

and increasing the educational opportunities of physical education in this regard are discussed by scientists B. Lowe, H. Slyusher, F. Keenon, A. Vett, E. Researched by Zadarko, J. Junger, Z. Barabas, D. Brown, A. Alpers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Sports aesthetics is a component of the philosophy of sophistication. Sports aesthetics studies the aesthetic content of sports, its place in the culture of society, and the interrelationship between sports and art, while studying the aesthetic laws in the field of sports. It analyzes the spiritual and aesthetic aspects of human physical development as a component of general culture. It can be seen that sport consists not only of fighting, fighting, and competitions, but also an aesthetic field that occupies an important place in social life and is embedded in the healthy lifestyle of a person. For example, people who practice Karate-do, one of the Eastern martial arts, not only master striking skills, the art of self-defense, learning to break objects, combat style and strategy, but also learn to improve the world and people. will be able to consciously change his way of life, perceiving the interdependence of all existing proportions and the aesthetic harmony with nature.

One of the components of education of a perfect personality is the aesthetic education of students in the process of physical education. Aesthetic education of students in the higher education system is an important component of this system. In this, all educational and training tools are used in harmony. In particular, aesthetic training of students through sports aesthetics in the process of physical training and extracurricular activities requires the formation of a number of educational and educational qualities. Among them, logically correct perception of the theory and history of sports aesthetics; correct understanding of professional sports performances and correct analysis and interpretation of their aesthetic aspects (sports aesthetics), understanding, imagination of any (creative, communicative, social) activity dedicated to sports, physical education, impressions; the formation of the need for personal participation in sports circles, branches, etc.; it is of particular importance to be able to consciously monitor certain elements of sports aesthetics, their general exercises, the aesthetics of performance of integrated performances, and mobilize them for personal improvement. For this, it is required that the students and the trainers who work with them are armed with the integration of knowledge related to aesthetic education. From this point of view, we found it necessary to study the situation of aesthetic education in our country in pedagogical theory and practice and to show the conclusions derived from it in this work.

In the history of Uzbekistan, the issue of aesthetic education has always been treated with special attention and respect. It is known that the desire of the Uzbek people to culturalize their lifestyle is reflected in their history, particularly in the history of applied and visual arts. This art was first manifested as the main criterion in the functions of life, in its aesthetics - to serve the beauty of people's lives. In this way, at one time they had an aesthetic effect on people as works of art.

In the study and analysis of the pedagogical theory of the issue of aesthetic education of students and youth in Uzbekistan, we have seen that there is a lot of fundamental research in this regard. In particular, the formation and development of the system of aesthetic education of students in Uzbekistan (by S.Kh. Fayzulina); in this process, the disclosure of such issues as the pedagogical foundations of the use of ancient artistic-aesthetic traditions (by S.K. Annamuratova) revealed a number of directions in the issue of aesthetic education of students and youth through physical education.

The fact that the research conducted in our country on the problems of aesthetic education of students is focused on its non-auditory forms gives specific recommendations regarding the content, methods, form, and tools of aesthetic education in non-auditory classes from physical education. The work performed on the aesthetic education of students in the circle classes of musical culture (A. Hasanov, F. Jorayev), visual and applied arts (A. Vasikov, A. Sulaymonov, K. Dosimov) with its theoretical and practical importance, it ensures a significant revival of work in this direction in our republic. At the moment, it is possible to draw analytical conclusions from the research conducted outside our country (A.I. Shakhova, I.F. Goncharov, L. Sakharov, T.B. Fridman) on the issue of aesthetic education of young people and use them in aesthetic education of the youth of our country. However, despite the fact that it is one of the most effective forms and directions of education and training outside the auditorium, the possibilities of physical training are not fully used.

In the course of classes outside the auditorium, a number of aspects can be introduced that are strictly required to be followed in the aesthetic education of teenagers in physical education. In other countries, in particular, in Poland, Russia and the Czech Republic, there are certain studies on the issue of aesthetic education of students through physical education. Among them, we can show the works devoted to a conversation with a trainer about education, getting to know beauty (N.Y.E.Shchurkova's aesthetic education in physical education classes), and physical health work (V.K.Shurukhina).

It is known that sports and physical education are almost always mentioned side by side, but they differ significantly from each other. Physical education mainly consists of mass exercises or sets of exercises aimed at ensuring human health, which all classes of society of different ages do voluntarily "for themselves". And sport, regardless of its field, includes individual or team competition of specially trained people, mostly young people, under the supervision of expert teachers. The aesthetic difference between sports and physical education is explained by the philosopher and scientist Abdulla Sher, who says that physical education, regardless of its form (individual or collective), rejects competition and allows a person to choose what he wants from different forms of exercise. In sports, the competition is in the first place, and certain exercises are performed in it. But this obligation allows the athlete to move freely within a certain type of sport, that is, creative approach in sports is not prohibited, but supported.

It should be noted that the most important problem in sports aesthetics is its similarity with art. Based on this, classical sports can be interpreted as a kind of art. In this regard, western scientists such as Rene Mayu, Maureen Kovich, Benjamin Lowe and many famous athletes express the opinion that sports can be accepted as art. The rules of sports and physical exercises are important for young people's strong acquisition in life. These rules essentially acquire moral and aesthetic content. Because sport serves to glorify and acquire moral values such as treating opponents with respect, strong faith in teachers and coaches, deep respect for referees and spectators, endurance, passion for victory, and honesty. at the same time, it also carries out works of education of taste by showing beautiful behavior, giving aesthetic pleasure to a person, and even aesthetic attitude to sports equipment.

Aesthetic analysis of pleasure in sports competitions and physical movements is one of the important tasks of sports aesthetics. Currently, sport is recognized as a very widespread cultural field around the world. This is especially evident in the case of Uzbekistan. With the honor of independence, we have formed a view of sports as an integral part of national culture, it has become customary to hold competitions in all its types, and Uzbek wrestling has received the status of a universal sport.

Today, it is positive that sports aesthetics are becoming a part of our healthy lifestyle. Be it sport or physical education, a healthy lifestyle cannot be formed without these two factors. Therefore, it is impossible to imagine a healthy lifestyle without sports aesthetics.

Sport, as a means of aesthetic education, has a special importance in the development of a modern person. Currently, the development of sports has risen to the level of state policy in our country. The main goal is to raise the generation to be physically strong, healthy, brave defenders of the motherland.

In recent years, the restoration of the rich cultural heritage of our people, the development of high spirituality, national identity and the existing centuries-old traditions of the people, to be physically healthy, intellectually mature and well-rounded. the necessary conditions for establishing a society of individuals were created. Systematic and specific goal-oriented measures were implemented to fully satisfy the cultural and aesthetic needs of the population and to develop physical education and mass sports. An effective system of training skilled athletes capable of adequately protecting the honor of Uzbekistan and achieving high goals in prestigious international competitions has been created. However, it is becoming urgent to eliminate the problems related to the further development and strengthening of the material and technical base of sports and health facilities, facilities and structures. Therefore, to improve the management system in the field of culture and sports, to fundamentally increase the effectiveness of the implementation of the state policy aimed at ensuring the further development of the rich and unique culture, art and creativity of the people of Uzbekistan in this field, The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 15, 2017 "On measures to further improve the management system in the field of culture and sports" was announced in order to strengthen the pursuit of spiritual and moral maturity and a healthy lifestyle. The decree stipulates the organization of large-scale work on the popularization of sports and physical education among the broad strata of the population, physical education and health, strengthening the material and technical base of sports organizations, encouraging children, especially girls, to regularly participate in sports. issues such as broad involvement in participation, comprehensive development of children's sports, increasing the quality of children's sports education, further expanding the network of children's sports facilities in all regions, strengthening children's health and ensuring their stable physical development main task and directions of activity are defined.

Today, the educational value of sports aesthetics is increasing more and more. Especially in recent years, sport has become popular in Uzbekistan at an unprecedented level. Currently, sports competitions are not just for winning, but as a condition for the manifestation of aesthetic qualities such as beauty and

grandeur, they attract viewers of different ages, they provide refinement of their free time. Aesthetic education is sometimes seen as a means of moral education of athletes, but these factors should be described as beauty in sports or aesthetic actions in the implementation of actions: in the first place, organization of sports events as a means of aesthetic education; in the second place, educational psychological processes of young athletes; in the third place, arbitration problems.

When organizing world sports competitions, the organizers pay attention to the decorative aspect of the event.

When sports competitions are organized, the beauty in it is enhanced by the individual skills of the athletes, but if their moral or psychological state is not perfect, it creates a state of dissatisfaction in the perception of the strange beauty to the audience. In this place, moral education is also important.

CONCLUSION. The large-scale and important role of sport in aesthetic education is that it affects people's feelings and emotions, and as a result of such an effect, psychological oppression occurs in the perceiver. Regular perception of a work of art leads to the opening of family and work problems, marriage complications, shortcomings and other hidden feelings in the soul. A person begins to believe that there is a miracle in this world. That is, sport has the power to renew the soul. At the same time, this spirit favors something because it is beautiful and glorious, and rejects something because it is ugly and base. It is at this point that sports educates a person in an ideological aspect: sports creates a person who is committed to the service of ideas and ideals from an individual who perceives himself with aesthetic pleasure.

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